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Hemp Club

Competent and Connected
Clusters Unfold the Hemp
Industry Potential for the
European Bioeconomy

European Cluster Excellence Programme with ClusterXchange scheme connecting ecosystem and cities
COS-CLUSTER-2020-3-03

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IMPLEMENTATION OF THE ClusterXchange PLATFORM DELIVERABLE 4.1

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SAT

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

As Work Package 4 aims to organize ClusterXchange visits for mutual learning and bioeconomy growth, this goal is to be realized with the help of a platform dedicated to hemp organizations, that could foster successful matches and collaborations between the operators of the hemp-based value chain. Therefore, in collaboration with WP5 (creation of the website) and WP2 (information on the European organisations operating in the hemp sectors), task 4.1 should implement this platform, also ensuring a connection with the ClusterXchange IT Tool provided by ECCP. The HempClub project proposes a special interactive interface map to be programmed in the project website with the aim of finding the best matching opportunities for organisations in the bioeconomy/hemp sector. This map should grow over the time beyond the boundaries of the current clusters' members and cover finally all European regions.

The platform shall map the organisations operating in the hemp sector at different steps of the value chain. The mapping of these organizations is based on several sources: desk research, mapping activity in WP2, voluntary addition of companies interested in the project, members of wide EU hemp networks.

In this context, the present deliverable details theoretically our concept, the methodology and the detailed steps that we plan to use for the implementation of the map, including the results of the mapping activity. The interactive map, implemented as described in detail in this deliverable, will be available online for public consultation on 31st October 2022. Meanwhile, users will be able to consult freely the database of hemp organizations mapped so far in the project.

Table of content

1. Introduction.....	4
1.1 Short summary of the initially activity.....	4
1.2 Stating the framework of the work and its objective.....	4
2. Results from mapping activity	5
2.1 Methodology	5
3. How to implement the map - Methodology and Decision finding.....	6
3.1 Layout requirements	7
3.2 Layout examples.....	8
Competence Atlas – SAT (Austria).....	8
Booking.com	9
Post Office Location Finder (Germany)	10
Mundraub (Germany).....	11
Clusterexzellenz in Germany	12
3.3 Open-Source Software and Base Map.....	15
Software	15
Base Map	15
3.4 How to implement the map?	16
4. Conclusion and Outlook	16
References.....	17

1. Introduction

The **Work Package 4** – ClusterXchange visits for mutual learning and bioeconomy growth - has two objectives: the assessment of the ClusterXchange activities and the management and implementation of the ClusterXchange mobility scheme. In this context, the WP should cover the promotion, recruitment, matching and follow-up of 80 short-term exchanges between target members of clusters located in other (EU and other COSME participating) countries. Furthermore, this WP is also responsible for the coordination of such exchanges between all the actors involved in the hemp-based value chain. These goals are to be realized with the help of a platform dedicated to hemp organizations, that could foster successful matches and collaborations between the operators of the hemp-based value chain. Thus, WP4 is based on 3 tasks:

Task 4.1 Implementation of the ClusterXchange platform

Task 4.2 Assessment of ClusterXchange applicants

Task 4.3 ClusterXchange building, management and development

The present report describes the activities carried out in T4.1, mainly the mapping of hemp organizations and the implementation of the HempClub interactive map

1.1 Short summary of the initially activity

For the implementation of the ClusterXChange mobility scheme, ECCP provides an IT Tool which shall be the only entry point for applications and administration of ClusterXchange, allowing the Partnership to monitor and treat all incoming requests easily. The tool also allows accepted participants to find matching organisations by using an online catalogue of hosting organisations registered in the IT tool. As this tool includes a lot of organizations operating in sectors that may be very different between one another, HempClub project proposes a special interactive interface map to be programmed in the project website with the aim of finding the best matching opportunities for organisations in the bioeconomy/hemp sector. The platform shall map the organisations operating in the hemp sector at different steps of the value chain (farmers/production, processing, distribution, retail). The mapping of these organizations is based on several sources (details are provided in paragraph 2.1): desk research, mapping activity in WP2, voluntary addition of companies interested in the project, members of wide EU hemp networks. Based on their value chain role, each organization shall be marked with a different icon to make the research more intuitive and user friendly (Proposal: 50)

Therefore, in collaboration with WP5 (creation of the website) and WP2 (information on the European organisations operating in the hemp sectors), task 4.1 should implement this platform, also ensuring a connection with the ClusterXchange IT Tool. This map should grow over the time beyond the boundaries of the current clusters' members and cover finally all European regions (Proposal: 51).

In this context, the present deliverable details theoretically our concept, the methodology and the detailed steps that we plan to use for the implementation of the map, including the results of the mapping activity. The interactive map, implemented as described in detail in this deliverable, will be available online for public consultation on 31st October 2022. Meanwhile, users will be able to consult freely the database of hemp organizations mapped so far in the project, as in Annex 1 of this deliverable.

1.2 Stating the framework of the work and its objective

While working on the task, it has become apparent that the IT tool ClusterXchange has some limitations that hindered the full implementation of exchanges. Because of this circumstance, at the present moment, it is not useful to focus the implementation of the ClusterXchange tool on the project webpage. Thus, we decide to implement only the interactive map on the project webpage without considering the

ClusterXchange tool now. In a further step, also taking into account the new released version of the IT Tool, we suggest including in the company organization information the link to their ClusterXchange profile page at the map directly, thus linking the HempClub map with the COSME tool.

However, the map will focus not only on organizations registered on the CXC IT Tool nor only on cluster members. The idea is to include as many hemp organizations as possible to create a comprehensive map that could facilitate the creation of new hemp-based value chains. At the same time, the platform will have a specific focus on hemp and green clusters (specific icon on the map) so that organizations that are still not a member of a cluster could find their best opportunity to become part of this network. For example, in Tirol (Austria) we have the Cluster Initiative “Competence Center Alpine Hemp 360°” which has about 40 players and is directly related to hemp and bioeconomy sectors. But in all it is more an unofficial network than a real cluster. Only 4 players are cluster members (Alpex, Wisperwhool, Syncraft, UIBK). Not even Salewa, which is a big player in the hemp sector, is a cluster member. Therefore, we suggest integrating both Cluster members and Competence carrier, considering the different affiliations in the way of illustration.

2. Results from mapping activity

The mapping activity carried out in this task aims at creating a comprehensive public database of organizations operating in the hemp sector acting as a point of reference for companies and other organizations that are searching for a partner or collaborations in the sector, including members-clusters relationship. Indeed, the industrial hemp landscape is very fragmented with many very small and small enterprises that have difficulties in finding the right partner for implementing their own business. For example, processing industries may find difficult to obtain the necessary quantity or the specific needed quality of hemp biomass; on the contrary, farmers and primary producers of hemp may be not able to sell all the biomass they produce. In this context, the database, and the subsequent interactive map that will be developed from the database, could represent a point of reference to build new, sustainable, and effective value chains based on hemp.

2.1 Methodology

The mapping activity was based on the combination of several sources:

1. Mapping activity on cluster members carried out in WP2 (D1.2), resulting in 85 organizations. The main contributions came from CZEHEMP and FEDERCANAPA members, as these two clusters have a specific focus on hemp (30 and 41 organizations respectively) and INDAGROPOL (36 organizations).
2. Desk research, based on primary sources such as the Italian Chamber of Commerce database. This analysis led to the identification of 86 organizations.
3. Voluntary additions of companies that were interested in our project and asked to be part of this database, including visiting organizations: 16 organizations in total.
4. Members of EU hemp networks such as members of the European Industrial Hemp Associations: 200 organizations in total.
5. Additional inputs from HempClub partners that are actively involved in hemp-based value chains: 75 organizations in total

The resulting database contains 330 entries, after crosschecking duplicates (as one organization may have resulted e.g., both from the mapping activity in 1 and desk research in 2). This database mainly includes Czech, Romanian and Italian organization as a result in the mapping methodology (main contributions from Czechemp and INDAGROPOL cluster and opportunity to access information from the Italian Chamber of

Commerce). However, the database is a living document that will be implemented during the entire project duration also including other EU countries outside the HempClub Partnership.

The information available for each organization are:

- Name
- Address
- Country
- Website
- Position in the value chain
- Focus/reference market
- Statute/type of organization

Further information will be included soon to match the requirements for the implementation of the interactive interface map as described in paragraph 3.1.

The resulting database is available as Annex 1 on this deliverable and will be published on the project website.

3. How to implement the map - Methodology and Decision finding

To find the best matching opportunities for organisations in the bioeconomy/hemp sector, a special interactive interface map shall be programmed. The platform shall map the organisations operating in the hemp sector (as identified with the mapping activity in WP2).

Figure 1 - Proposed structure for the interactive map as proposed in the Grant Agreement

The implementation of the interactive map must be feasible from an economic point of view while be as user friendly and effective as possible. Taking into account this base principle, the following issues need to be defined for the successful implementation of the interactive map:

- Base map
- Layout
- Software
- Host and Operator

The interactive map will be built also taking into account these two crucial elements:

- The useful life of the map: entire duration of the project and at least 2 years after the project ends to ensure the long lasting impact of the HempClub project;
- The operator of the map: SAT will manage the implementation of the platform for its entire life.

3.1 Layout requirements

Based on their position in the value chain and their role, each organization shall be marked with a different icon (Proposal: 50) (Figure 1). The proposed categories to classify the mapped organizations are the following (Figure 1).

- Agriculture and raw material production
- Raw material processing
- Product development and processing (industrial uses)
- Services for the industry
- Machineries and Equipment
- Waste management, recycling, upcycling
- Research and Education

These categories may vary during the project based on the feedback we will receive on the user friendliness of the map.

In the first step of the implementation, the different topics will be summarized into 4 main areas, in order to simplify the user friendliness of the platform. These areas will be displayed as icons:

- **Agriculture** [Farmers, seeds, harvester, contract harvesting, machinery ring with equipment, etc.]
- **Production** [Harvesting processes, refining, fabrication semi-finished products, industrial production, etc.]
- **Research and Development** [Research Institutes, product development, etc.]
- **Consulting Services**

The icons lead to further information and contact possibilities. For each organization, this information will be included (if available):

- Name
- Location
- Cluster (if they are members of a cluster)
- Reference market/focus
- Position in the value chain
- Type of organization (Large Enterprise, SME, NGO, etc)
- Website link
- Public contact information (such as the ones we can find on google or on the webpage)
- Link to the ECCP organizations webpage (if available)
- Company Logo

Further we must decide in which way this information shall be presented: as pop-up-window (Fig. 2 on the left) or as extra sheet (Fig. 2 on the right).

Figure 2- Left – This example shows the pop-up-window option at the German Post Office location finder [1], Right – The Competence Atlas published by SAT use an extra sheet to show the detailed organization information [2]

This information can be presented in different formats. The options that have been studied by SAT, as the partner responsible for this activity, are presented in the paragraphs below.

3.2 Layout examples

Competence Atlas – SAT (Austria)

In the Competence Atlas (<https://www.standort-tirol.at/cluster/kompetenzatlas> [3]), the member directory of the cluster initiatives of SAT, all cluster members are shown on the Tyrol map (Fig. 3 top) with a detailed description of the respective company activity, special competencies, and specializations as well as the cluster affiliation. Cluster members thus not only receive additional visibility, but also effective support in the search for suitable cooperation partners. The entry in the Competence Atlas is reserved only for cluster members, but the use of the Competence Atlas is open to everyone who wants to get an overview. Cluster members can be found in the Tyrol map directly or in a search mask. By clicking on a cluster member entry in the list below or in the map, users can access detailed information on that member (Fig. 3 button). Although the Competence Atlas is well structured, this solution can be very expensive as the tool is not SAT's property.

Figure 3 – Layout structure of the Competence Atlas published by the SAT (top [3], bottom [2])

Booking.com

The booking.com [4] platform is structured in different “pins” on a map that identify different locations (Fig. 4). By clicking on the “pin”, a pop-up window provides summary information on the entry located in that location. It is then possible to click on a link to obtain further information on the entry. The platform

bookin.com has an attractive and usable layout that we would like to transfer to our interactive project map. Therefore, we have been on the lookout for similar platforms to find further inspiration for the implementation, as the German Post office location finder and the German platform Mundraub that are described below.

Figure 4 – Structure of the platform Booking.com [4]

Post Office Location Finder (Germany)

The German Post office location finder ([https://www.post.at/en/sf/locationfinder\[1\]](https://www.post.at/en/sf/locationfinder[1])) is structured in a similar way of the booking.com platform. Each "pin" on the map stands for one post location (Fig. 5). By clicking on the "pin", a pop-up window provides summary information on the post location information in a pop-up window. To implement this map, the open-source software Leaflet (see 3.3) was used with Google Maps as base map. As it uses an open-source software, it could represent an excellent example to implement the HempClub map.

Figure 5 - Layout option of the German Post Office Location Finder [1]

Mundraub (Germany)

The mundraub.org platform is for everyone who discovers native fruit, nuts, and herbs in public spaces. The people engage with each other both online and in real life to share finds, carry out joint planting and harvesting activities, or exchange ideas in regional groups. This platform has a similar layout as Booking.com. Each “pin” in the map (<https://mundraub.org/map> [5]) represents an edible plant in a public space. In the first bullet level the icon of the pin shows the type of the plant. In a second bullet level the plant types are divided into classes which can be filtered the on the left side of the page (Fig. 6 top). Information about the different public spaces can be discovered by mouse click. The details are then provided as an extra sheet in the same tab (Fig. 6 bottom). To implement this map the open-source software Leaflet (see 3.3) was used with Open Street Maps as base map.

Figure 6 – Structure of the platform mundraub.org and its possibilities to present information (top [5], bottom [6])

Clusterexzellenz in Germany

This layout option shows the platform Clusterexzellenz in Germany ("go-cluster" program) that is available on the homepage of the Federal Ministry of Economics and Climate Protection: <https://www.clusterplattform.de/CLUSTER/Navigation/Karte/SiteGlobals/Forms/Formulare/karte-formular.html> [7]. This map provides a quick overview of where the best clusters and cluster management organizations are located regionally and in which industries and technology fields they operate. Under "Filter options" there are various search criteria so that targeted searches can be made for clusters and cluster management organizations in specific industries and technology fields, federal states and for measures of excellence. Each "pin" stands for one of the clusters including the cluster management organization. Further information can be discovered by mouse click (Fig. 9 top). A short organization information is available by clicking at each "pin" (Fig. 9 middle). The detailed information for each pin is provided as an extra sheet in a separate tab (Fig. 9 bottom).

The screenshot displays the 'Clusterexzellenz in Deutschland' web interface. At the top, there is a header with the logo, contact information (phone: 030 310078-387, email: info@clusterplattform.de), and a 'STARTSEITE' button. Below the header, a search bar is present with the text 'Suchbegriff, Ort, PLZ...'. The main content area is divided into three sections: a list of clusters on the left, a map of Germany in the center, and filter options on the right. The list on the left shows three clusters: 'BioCon Valley' (Friedrich-Barnewitz-Straße 8, 18119 Rostock), 'Cluster Ernährung am Kern' (Hofer Straße 20, 95326 Kulmbach), and 'GIQS e. V. – Grenzüberschreitende Integrierte Qualitätssicherung e. V.' (Marie-Curie-Straße 3, 53359 Rheinbach). The map shows pins for these clusters: BioCon Valley in Rostock, Cluster Ernährung am Kern in Kulmbach, and GIQS in Rheinbach. The filter options on the right include 'Exzellenz-Maßnahme' and 'Technologiefeld'. The 'Technologiefeld' list includes various categories such as Automotive (32), Bauwirtschaft (3), Biotechnologie (17), Chemiewirtschaft (4), Dienstleistungen (20), Digitalisierung (40), Elektrotechnik (10), Energietechnologien (16), Ernährungswirtschaft (5), Forst- und Holzwirtschaft (1), Gesundheitswirtschaft (18), Industrie 4.0 (30), IuK-Technologien (24), Kreativwirtschaft (3), Kunststofftechnologien (7), Logistik (8), Luftfahrttechnologien (8), Medizintechnik (24), Messtechnik (2), Metallverarbeitung (3), Mikrosystemtechnik (7), Nanotechnologien (11), Optische Technologien und Photonik (13), Pflanzenforschung (3), and Produktionstechnologien (25). A green arrow on the left side of the image points from the text above to the screenshot.

Clusterexzellenz in Deutschland

HABEN SIE FRAGEN?
 ☎ 030 310078-387 ✉ info@clusterplattform.de

✖ LISTE 3 Einträge 🔍 Suchbegriff, Ort, PLZ...

← zurück zur Liste

➔ [STARTSEITE](#)

BioCon Valley®

BioCon Valley® **Exzellenz-Maßnahmen**
 go-cluster, Silber-Label nach ECEI

Technologiefelder
 Biotechnologie, Medizintechnik,
 Digitalisierung, Gesundheitswirtschaft,
 Pflanzenforschung

Lars Bauer
 ☎ +49 381-650 70 90 ✉ info@bcv.org
 📍 Friedrich-Barnewitz-Straße 6, 18119 Rostock
 🌐 <http://www.bcv.org/startseite/>

🗨 [ZUR DETAILSICHT](#)

✖ **FILTEROPTIONEN**

Exzellenz-Maßnahme ▾

Technologiefeld ▴

- Automotive (32)
- Bauwirtschaft (3)
- Biotechnologie (17)
- Chemiewirtschaft (4)
- Dienstleistungen (20)
- Digitalisierung (40)
- Elektrotechnik (10)
- Energietechnologien (16)
- Ernährungswirtschaft (5)
- Forst- und Holzwirtschaft (1)
- Gesundheitswirtschaft (18)
- Industrie 4.0 (30)
- IuK-Technologien (24)
- Kreativwirtschaft (3)
- Kunststofftechnologien (7)
- Logistik (8)
- Luftfahrttechnologien (8)
- Medizintechnik (24)
- Messtechnik (2)
- Metalverarbeitung (3)
- Mikrosystemtechnik (7)
- Nanotechnologien (11)
- Optische Technologien und Photonik (13)
- Pflanzenforschung (3)
- Produktionstechnologien (25)

BioCon Valley®

BioCon Valley® ist die Initiative für Life Science und Gesundheitswirtschaft in Mecklenburg-Vorpommern. Als zentraler Ansprechpartner und Dienstleister unterstützen wir die Akteure in den Branchen und engagieren uns für die wirtschaftliche und wissenschaftliche Profilierung des Standortes Mecklenburg-Vorpommern.

Das Cluster

Die Kernkompetenzen des Netzwerkes liegen in den Bereichen Gesundheitswirtschaft, Biowissenschaften, Medizin und Medizintechnik, Molekularbiologie, Plasmaphysik, Neurowissenschaften und Onkologie, der Tiergesundheit und der Pflanzenzüchtung sowie deren Nutzung in der Bioökonomie, in eHealth, der gesunden Ernährung und dem Gesundheitstourismus.

Gesundheitswirtschaft und Life Science haben für den Wirtschafts- und Wissenschaftsstandort Mecklenburg-Vorpommern herausragende Bedeutung. Fast 20 Prozent beträgt der Anteil der Branche am Arbeitsmarkt des Landes, bei fast 15 Prozent und damit über dem Bundesdurchschnitt liegt ihr Anteil an der Bruttowertschöpfung des Landes. Entsprechend intensiv wird die weitere Entwicklung und Ausdifferenzierung durch das Land begleitet. Grundlage dafür bildet der „Masterplan Gesundheitswirtschaft 2020“. Seine Umsetzung wird durch das von der Landesregierung berufene Kuratorium Gesundheitswirtschaft als Ideen- und Impulsgeber moderiert und von BioCon Valley koordiniert. Ziel ist es, Mecklenburg-Vorpommern zum führenden Gesundheitsland in Deutschland zu entwickeln

Leistungen und Angebote

Netzwerkmanagement und Branchenmonitoring

BioCon Valley fördert den Dialog zwischen den Akteuren aus Wirtschaft, Wissenschaft und Politik mit dem Ziel, Kompetenzen zu vernetzen und Zusammenarbeit und Projekte zu initiieren. Eine wesentliche Grundlage dafür stellt die Beobachtung und Analyse der Branchenentwicklung dar, die ebenfalls von BioCon Valley begleitet wird.

Projektitinierung und -begleitung

BioCon Valley unterstützt Forscher und Unternehmen beim Wissenstransfer, bei der Projekteinwerbung sowie beim Management von Projekten mit dem Ziel, dass Firmen die hervorragend entwickelte Wissenschaftslandschaft in der Region besser nutzen und Mecklenburg-Vorpommern als Wirtschaftsstandort gestärkt wird. Darüber hinaus entwickelt und realisiert BioCon Valley für öffentliche und private Auftraggeber eigenständige Projekte.

Internationalisierung

BioCon Valley begleitet und betreut Unternehmen und Institutionen bei ihren Internationalisierungsaktivitäten. Dazu zählt die Präsentation von Region und Branchen bei internationalen Messen, die Organization und Begleitung von Wirtschaftsdelegationen wie die Erstellung maßgeschneiderter Angebote für die Branche sowie die Vermittlung von Kontakten in Wissenschaft und Wirtschaft.

Öffentlichkeitsarbeit und Veranstaltungen

BioCon Valley betreibt aktive Öffentlichkeitsarbeit und Standortwerbung für Mecklenburg-Vorpommern als Forschungs- und Wirtschaftsstandort für Life Science und Gesundheitswirtschaft. Dafür organisiert das Cluster zahlreiche Fachveranstaltungen, wie u.a., die Nationale Branchenkonferenz Gesundheitswirtschaft. Mit seinen mehr als 700 Teilnehmern hat sich dieses im Auftrag des Landes Mecklenburg-Vorpommern organisierte Forum des Gesundheitssektors national und international als Schaufenster der Branche etabliert.

Ansprechpartner

Lars Bauer
Friedrich-Barnewitz-Straße 8
18119 Rostock
T +49 381-650 70 90
Per E-Mail kontaktieren

Weiterführende Informationen

↳ ClusterERFOLG: Guten Morgen, Gesundheitswirtschaft!

↳ BioCon Valley®

 Zur Landkarte

Informationen zum Innovationscluster:

Mitglieder / Clusterakteure

- Anzahl insgesamt: 124
- kleine und mittlere Unternehmen: 49
- Großunternehmen: 1
- Universitäten und Hochschulen: 4
- außeruniversitäre Forschungseinrichtungen: 6
- Technologie- und Innovationsparks: 2
- sonstige Organisationen: 62

Schlüsselselakteure

Forschungs- / Produktfelder

- Medizintechnik
- Marine Biotechnologie
- Personalisierte Medizin
- E-Health
- Bioökonomie

Beschäftigte im Clustermanagement: 16

Gründungsjahr der Organisation: 2001

Exzellenz-Maßnahmen und Auszeichnungen

[Quelle: ESCA]

Seite empfehlen:

 Druckansicht

Figure 7 – Structure of the German platform Clusterexzellenz and its possibilities to present information (Top and middle [7], bottom [8])

3.3 Open-Source Software and Base Map

We suggest using the combination of the Open-Source Software Leaflet and OpenStreetMap as base map, such as the one used for the mundraub.org platform. OpenStreetMap is independent an open-data project and the data itself can be used free of charge. This solution is perfect from an economic point of view and easy to operate by anyone.

Software

Leaflet (<https://leafletjs.com/>) [9] is an open-source JavaScript library that can be used to create WebGIS applications/ for (mobile-friendly) interactive maps. The library uses HTML5, CSS3 and thus supports most desktop and mobile browsers. Leaflet can be used to easily present web map tile services along with custom geodata on a web page. Interactive features such as pop-ups can be added to the geodata. Leaflet supports Web Map Service (WMS), Web Map Tile Service (WMTS), GeoJSON, image overlays. Other types of layers or geodata formats can be included via plug-ins (KML, CSV, WKT, GPX, ...). Leafletjs supports Chrome, Firefox, Safari 5+, Opera 12+, Internet Explorer 7-11 and Microsoft Edge [<https://leafletjs.com/#features>, 21.09.2022]. It “is designed with *simplicity, performance, and usability* in mind. It works efficiently across all major desktop and mobile platforms, can be extended with lots of [plugins](#), has a beautiful, easy to use and [well-documented API](#) and a simple, readable [source code](#) that is a joy to [contribute](#) to” [9].

WordPress (<https://de.wordpress.org/> [10]) would be a further interesting open-source tool which has several WordPress map plugin options. However, a Wordpress map is only "worthwhile" if the interactive map is also to be integrated on a Wordpress webpage. An in-depth discussion with the web developer should be organized to further discuss this option.

Base Map

For our interactive map, we can use Google Maps or Open Street Map as base map.

OpenStreetMap (OSM) is a free project whose map material and the underlying geodata can be used under an open-source license. The geodata is freely usable in a database for use by anyone (Open Data). Both commercial and free maps can be created from this data. The data can continue to be used free of charge in print or on websites, without being limited by restrictive licenses. According to the license, the citation of OpenStreetMap as the data source and the subordination of the modification of the dataset under the same license is required [11, 12, 13].

Google Maps is a mapping service developed by Google. For a long time, Google Maps has been the standard for map services and route planning on the web. Since the DSGVO came into force, the integration of Google Maps into a website is only possible with a data protection notice and the explicit consent of the user. This is mandatory because the map view only works via the live retrieval of data from the Google servers and thus, conversely, user data is transferred to Google when the map is displayed. Currently, the display of a map view without advanced features is free of charge, regardless of the number of page views. However, this can change, and Google can also adjust its terms of use and business conditions at very short notice. OpenStreetMap, on the other hand, is independent as an open data project, and the data itself can be used free of charge [12, 13].

3.4 How to implement the map?

A further task area is to decide in which way the interactive map shall be implemented. The two available options for the implementation are:

1. Check what possibility gives us the program which was used for the creation of the project webpage. Is there already a tool to implement the map directly in the project webpage?
2. Develop the map on a separate webpage and add the link of this webpage to the project website.

The latter option seems the most feasible from a technical point of view as the website is not managed internally by the HempClub Partnership but by an external subcontractor (see D4.1). However, an in-depth discussion with the Developer will be initiated to evaluate the technical feasibility of the first solution.

Further, we must decide, at which location and in which format should the data (marker locations and content of the popups) be stored. If the data is included in the definition (source code) of the interactive map, subsequent changes to the data require access to the website host and basic programming knowledge. If the data is stored in an external text file, only the text file needs to be changed. The text file may be stored at the website host or an external host.

4. Conclusion and Outlook

During the entire duration of the project, the map will be continuously implemented by searching new sources (additional networks, analysis of Chamber of Commerce data from other countries, etc..) and relying on voluntary additions of companies and organizations we may have contacts with.

Meanwhile, based on the technical information and requirements described in this deliverable, SAT will implement the interactive interface map that will be available online for public consultation on 31st October 2022.

Following a co-creation approach, the database and the resulting interactive map will continuously be updated in their content but also in their form. Users will be able to:

- Ask to be added in the map if not already included
- Provide feedback on the user friendliness of the platform
- Provide feedback on the content and request to add new information on organizations

This feedback will be essential to ensure the effectiveness of the HempClub platform in building hemp-based value chains.

References

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Name	Address	Country	Website	Focus	statute
A.R. Canapa	Via Toscana 119, 40141 - Bologna	IT		hemp production	
AGREJA	Kvamo st. 9, Mokolų village, Marijampole municipality	LT	https://agreja.lt/	machinery	SME
Agricoltura canapa	Via Nostra Signora del Dolori 13, 18036 - San Biagio della Cima (IMPERIA)	IT		hemp production	
Agrii canapa	Via del Brentino 81, 55049 Viareggio (LUCCA)	IT		hemp production	
Agritec	Zemědělská 2520/16, 787 01 ŠUMPERK	CZ	https://www.agritec.cz/	hemp cultivation	LE
Agrochanvre	La Prise Gontier de Haut, 50 720 BARENTON	FR	https://www.agrochanvre.fr/	hemp building material, fil	SME
Alchemy farm	Via Paolo Borsellino 1/C, 42019 Arceto RE, Italy	IT	https://cbd-alchemy.com/it	CBD products	SME
Allive	Jovaru g. 3, Kaunas 47192	LT	http://allive.com/	hemp food & feed	
Annabis	Šlechtitelů 813/21, 779 00 Olomouc	CZ	www.annabis.cz	hemp cosmetics	SME
APLK - Asociace pěstitelů léčebného konopí, z.s.	Ve Smečkách 1258/6110 00 Praha 1	CZ		Lobby organization for ca	NGO
AROMA PLANT SRL	FURCULESTI; Teleorman	RO	aroma-plant.ro	CBD product	SME
Asociatia Fermierilor (Farmers Association)	B-dul Mărăști nr.61, Sector 1,București	RO	asociatiafermierilor.ro/	hemp farming	NGO
Industrialia (National Association of Industrial Association Ivan Patzaichin - Mila 23		RO	caneparo.org	hemp farming	NGO
Association Lin et Chanvre Bio	271 impasse d'Artemare - 76450 Saint Vaast Dieppedalle	FR	https://linetchanvrebio.org	hemp fibre, hemp textiles	NGO
ASSOCIATION REGINNOVA NE	IASI, Calea Chisinaului, nr.57, Postal code 700179	RO	www.reginnova.org/	hemp textile	NGO
Azienda agricola mele	Contrada Coste 20, 03030 - Posta Fibreno (FR)	IT	www.aziendagricolamele.it	hemp production	
Azienda agricola Canapa in fiore	Piazza della Motta 7, 21100 - Varese	IT	https://www.lassodeifiori.it	hemp production	
Azienda agricola DFG Canapa Filiera Italiana S.r.l	Via Codignole 45, 25124 - Brescia	IT		hemp production	SME
Azienda val di canapa	Molino dell'Avvocato 2 - 13835 - Valdilana (BI)	IT		hemp production	
BAFA Neu GmbH	Stephanstraße 2, 76316 Malsch	D	http://www.bafa-gmbh.de/	hemp food & feed	
Becanex gmbh	James-Franck-Straße 13, 12489 Berlin, Germany	DE	https://www.becanex.com/	CBD products	SME
Bio canapa	Via Roccastrada 2, 58100 - Grosseto (GR)	IT		hemp production	SS
Bioactif	1 All. du Parc de Mesemena, 44500 La Baule-Escoublac, France	FR	https://bioactif.eu/	CBD products	SME
BioBloom	Frauenkirchenerstr. 12, 7143 Apetlon, Austria	AT	https://biobloom.at	hemp food and cosmetics	
Biotech&Food	Frazione Noceno, Bellano (LC) 23822	IT	https://www.biotechandfoc	hemp industry support	SME
BioVita Group s.r.o.	Na Bečvě 1394751 31 Lipník nad Bečvou	CZ	www.biovitagroup.com	Hemp flowers, cannabino	SME
Bonaglia tessitura lino e canapa	Via Martiri della Libertà 117, 13888 - Mongrando (BI)	IT		hemp production	
BRAHAM & MURRAY GOOD HEMP,	Collabear Farm, Tawstock, Barnstaple, N Devon, EX31 3JZ	UK	https://www.goodhemp.co	hemp food and CBD	
CALORIS GROUP SA	Șoseaua Berceni Nr.8A, București 041914	RO	caloris.ro	Machinery	SME
Canah	Strada Josif Vulcan 22, Salonta 415500, Rumunsko	RO	https://www.canah.com	hemp food	
Canapa & territorio	Via Roma 77, 53100 - Siena	IT		consulting	SME
Canapa Bank	Via al Molino 1/23C, 10093 - Collegno (TO)	IT		CBD import/export	SS
Canapa Bio Italia	Via Giambologna 31, 50132 - Firenze (FI)	IT	www.canapabioitalia.com	hemp production	SME
Canapa campana	Corso Garibaldi 38, 80021 - Afragola (NA)	IT	https://canapacampana.eu	hemp production	SME
Canapa company	Via Togliatti 24, 06064 - Panicale (PG)	IT		CBD products selling	SME
Canapa della Salute	Via Olmo 10, 14054 - Castagnole delle Lanze (AT)	IT	www.canapadellasalute.it	Animal feed	SME
Canapa dell'alcantara	Contrada Mazzacchina Sottano, 95011 - Catalabiano (CT)	IT			SME
Canapa di maremma	Via Aquileia 76, 58100 - Grosseto (GR)	IT		hemp production	SS
Canapa di sardegna	Via Ponente 32, 09170 - Oristano (OR)	IT	www.canapadisardegna.it	hemp production	PERSON
Canapa di Terra d'otrantano	Via Moricino 11, 73100 - Lecce (LE)	IT		hemp production	
Canapa e canapa	Corso Aurelio Saffi 25/b, 48018 - Faenza (RA)	IT	https://cbweed-shop-faenz	selling CBD formulations	
Canapa elite	Via s. Nazaro 25, 37129 - Verona (VR)	IT	https://canapaelite.wixsite	hemp production and gro: SME	
Canapa factory	Via dei Sanniti 37, 86021 - Bojano (CB)	IT		hemp production and selling	
Canapa farm	Via Martiri Ungheresi 12, 03011 - Alatri (FR)	IT	www.canapafarm.eu	hemp product selling	
Canapa house	Viale Ceccarini 130, 47838 - Riccione (RI)	IT			
Canapa Hub	Piazza Invrea 8/12, 16123 - Genova (GE)	IT		hemp production	SME
Canapa Italia S.r.l.	Via Seveso 1, 20095 - Cusano Milanino (MI)	IT	https://www.cannabislegal	selling CBD formulations	PERSON
Canapa King	Via Lazzaro Palazzi 4, 20124 - Milano (MI)	IT	https://www.canapa-king.c	selling CBD formulations	SME
Canapa km0	Località Ponte ai Pini 15, 55011 - Altopascio (LU)	IT		hemp production	PERSON
Canapa lucana	Via Pertini 3, 85015 - Oppido Lucano (PT)	IT	www.canapalucana.it	proddessing and selling	SME
Canapa Meleretum	Via Divisione Julia 24, 33036 - Mereto di Tomba (UD)	IT		hemp oil extraction	SME

Canapa per te	Via del Banco di Santo 48, 00186 - Roma	IT	CBD and ricreative hemp	SME
Canapa Roma	Circonvalazione Cornelia 115, 00167 - Roma (RM)	IT	CBD and ricreative hemp	SME
Canapa Vallecamonica	Via Palla 16, 25040 - Angolo Terme (BS)	IT	food, cosmetics from can:	PERSON
Canapa venture	Via Ravenna 8, 00161 - Roma (RM)	IT	hemp products selling	SME
Canapa world	Strada Cesanense 174, 61040 - Monte Porzio (PU)	IT	hemp production	SS
Canapa's club	Via Imbriani 266, 95128 - Catania (CT)	IT	CBD products selling	SS
Canax	Viale Stelvio, 45, 20159 Milano MI, Italy	IT	https://canax.com/ hemp food, cosmetics, ph	SME
Candropharma	Industrieweg 11, 5731 HP Mierlo, THE NETHERLANDS	NL	https://candropharm.com/ CBD products, hemp flow	SME
Canebe s.r.o.	Rybná 716/24110 00 Praha 1	CZ	https://kanavape.eu/cs/o-r Hemp flowers, cannabino	SME
Caneparo cluster	150 Uranus Str, The Ark Building, Bucharest, 050827	RO	https://m.facebook.com/cz association	NGO
Caneparo cluster	150 Uranus Str, The Ark Building, Bucharest, 050827	RO	caneparo.org supply chain	NGO
Cannabric	Cañada Ojeda, 8, E-18500 Guadix	ES	http://www.cannabric.com hemp building	
Cannactiva	Placa d'Osca, 6, 08014 Barcelona, Spain	SP	https://cannactiva.com/ CBD products, hemp flow	SME
Cannaderm	Roháčova 188/37, Praha, 130 00	CZ	https://www.cannaderm.cz hemp cosmetics	LE
CannaFamily a.s.	Revoluční 1202/20110 00 Praha 1	CZ	www.cannacare.cz Hemp flowers	SME
Cannhelp	Stuwerstrasse 23, 1020 Vienna	AT	https://cannhelp.com/ CBD products	LE
Canva salus	Via Cristoforo Colombo 64, 35043 Monselice (PD)	IT	https://www.canvasalusrl.it R&D, hemp seeds	SME
Cavac	Le Fief Chapitre 85400 Saint Gemme La Plaine	FR	https://www.cavac-bioma hemp fibre, building mate	SME
CAVVAS	Str. Tautului Nr. 232A , Ap.5, Floresti 407280 , Cluj	RO	https://cavvas.com hemp fibre, hemp textile	
CB21 Pharma s.r.o.	Přívozní 1054/2, 170 00 Praha 7 – Holešovice	CZ	https://www.canneff.com hemp cosmetics	SME
CBD Oil Europe	Voltaweg 11D, 4382 NG Vlissingen, the Netherlands	NL	https://www.cbdoileurope.nl CBD products	SME
CBDepot s.r.o.	Masarykova třída 1595/54,,CZ-41501 Teplice, Czech republic	CZ	https://www.cbdepot.eu/ CBD products	SME
CELESA	Carrer Tuset, 10, 08006 Barcelona – SPAIN	ES	https://www.celesa-pulp.cc hemp paper	
Cellulosa innovativa canapa	Piazza Buenos Aires, 00198 - Roma (RM)	IT	paper and fibers producti	SME
Centro operativo sviluppo canapa del sud	Corso Giuseppe Garibaldi 38, 80021 - Afragola (NA)	IT	hemp production	SME
Česká zemědělská univerzita v Praze	Kamýcká 129, 165 00 Praha - Suchbát	CZ	www.czu.cz Cannabis flowers	UNI
Chanvriere	Route de Grange l'Evêque10180 SAINT LYE	FR	http://lachanvriere.com/en hemp building material, fc	SME
Chiaromonte canapa consapevole	Corso Aldo Moro 113, 90031 - Belmonte Mezzagno (PA)	IT	textile production	SME
Chris Carter	Londýnská 258/24120 00 Praha 2	CZ	import product from US	Hemp flowers PERSON
Cibidex	sp. Z oo ul. Stanisława Leszczyńskiego 4/29 50-078 Wrocław Poland	PL	cibidex.pl Cannabinoids	SME
CIDS FRANCE	17 Rue Paul Valery 47200 Marmande	FR	https://cids-grossiste-cbd.fr CBD based products selli	SME
Cilento Canapa	Via Andrea de Hippolytis 58/A, 84078 - Vallo della Lucania (SA)	IT	hemp production	SME
COLIBRID	Grand rue 64 CH-1196 Gland	FR	harbl.com CBD based products proc	SME
Compagnia della canapa	Via De Gasperi 79, 26812 - Borghetto Lodigiano (LO)	IT	CBD and ricreative hemp	SME
COMPLETE HEMP TECHNOLOGIES	Poniatowskiego 49, Jaroslaw	PL	completehemptechnologie hemp processing plants	SME
COMSPRY	20-22 Wenlock Road, London, England, N1 7GU	GB	comspry.com consulting	SME
Consorzio Marche canapa	Via Giovanni XXIII 45, 62100 - Macerata (MC)	IT		NGO
Consorzio nazionale tutela canapa italiana	Corso Savona 121, 14100 - Asti (AT)	IT		NGO
<u>Construire En Chanvre</u>	France	FR	http://www.construire-en-c hemp building	SME
Coop canapa	Località Stigliano 43, 62027 - San Severino Marche (MC)	IT	hemp production	SOC. COOP.
Cooperativa esercenti canapa italiana	Corso Savona 121, 14100 - Asti (AT)	IT		SOC. COOP.
Cormatex	Via Parugiano di Sotto, 152/166, 59013 Montemurlo PO	IT	https://www.cormatex.it/ hemp fibre, machinery	SME
Cretes	169 Bissegemstraat, 8560 Wevelgem, Belgium	BE	https://www.cretes.be/nl/cr machinery	
CRYSTAL	VIA CORRADO II IL SALICO 4, 20141, MILANO	IT	crystalweed.it cannabis online	SME
DACIA PLANT SRL	STRADA HARMANULUI NR. FN, 507015 BOD	RO	daciaplant.ro CBD product	SME
DASERE	33 Nikolaou Nikolaides, Kleanthis Savva Ct, Office 8, 8010 Paphos, Cyprus	CY	dasere.eu cultivation	SME
DBH Technologies s.r.o.	Československých legií 229, 439 01 Černčice	CZ	www.dbh-technologies.cz Hemp seeds	SME
DCCommunication	Str. Uranus 150, București 050826, Romania	RO	caneparo.org hemp advisory and supp	SME
DE IONESCU	Tabără 1A, Bistrița, Bistrița-Năsăud	RO	https://deionescu.com hemp textile	
Deep Nature Project	Untere Hauptstraße 168, 7122 Gols, Austria	AT	http://www.deepnatureproj hemp food, extract, cosmetics	
DEEP NATURE PROJECT	Untere Hauptstraße 168, A-7122 Gols, Austria	AT	deepnatureproject.com food, cosmetics from can:	SME
Delibutus s.r.o.	Masarykova 624/332, Ústí nad Labem - Bukov 400 01	CZ	https://www.delibutus.cz hemp cosmetics	SME
Drumparam	8233 Lafnitz 120, Oststeiermark	AT	https://www.drumparam.at music instrumets	SME

Dunagro	Raadhuisweg 11, 9665 JE, Oude Pekela	NL	http://dunagrohempgroup	Hemp flowers, cannabino LE	
DUTCH NATURAL HEALING	Pater Zen Productions BV webshop PO Box 193 1900 AD Castricum	NL	dutchnaturalhealing.com	CBD based products proc	Person
Eco canapa sicilia	Via Imbriani 253, 95128 - Catania (CT)	IT		hemp production	PERSON
EcoFuel Laboratories s.r.o.	Ocelářská 9, 190 00 Praha 9	CZ	www.ecofuel.cz	Hemp flowers, hemp food	SME
ECOINSUL s.r.o.	Nový Zlíchov 3172/6, 150 00 Praha 5	CZ	www.ecoinsul.eu	Hemp fibre - insolation	SME
ECOMAX	Calea Făgăraşului 59, Braşov 500053, Romania	RO	caneparo.org	hemp farming, advisory	SME
EIR HEALTH	Poznan	PL	eirhealth.com	CBD based products proc	SME
ELICAN	Parc Eurasanté, 70 rue du Dr Yersin 59120 LOOS	FR	elican.fr	innovations focusing on T	SME
ENDOWER	Alexanderplatz 1 10178 Berlin	DE	cbdwelt.de	CBD based products proc	SME
ENECTA	Corantijnstraat 5 - Amsterdam NL	NL	enecta.com	CBD based products proc	SME
Erba birdes isola della canapa	Località Cortiois, 09010 - San Giovanni Suergiu (SU)	IT		CBD and ricreative hemp	SME
ESSENTIA PURA	Dunajska Cesta 196, 1000 Ljubljana	SLO	essentiapura.com	Hemp Extraction, White L	SME
Essenze di canapa	Viale Monsignore Secondo Bologna 16/C, 86100 - Campobasso (CB)	IT		food, cosmetics from can:	SME
Estonian Organic Protein Cooperation	Vabriku 3a, Vahi, Tartumaa, Estonia, 60534	ET	www.orgestprotein.eu	hemp food	
ESTONIAN ORGANIC PROTEIN COOPERATION	Vabriku 3a, Vahi, Tartumaa	EST	www.orgestprotein.eu	cultivation	SME
Eurochanvre	7, route de Dijon, 70 100 ARC LES GRAY	D	http://www.eurochanvre.eu	hemp fibre, building mate	SME
European Hemp Industry Association	Rue du Commerce 31, 1000 Brussels, Belgium	BE	https://eiha.org	International hemp	
Fakultní nemocnice u sv. Anny v Brně - ICRC	Pekařská 664/53, 656 91 Brno	CZ	www.fnusa.cz	Cannabis flowers	PLC
FALTIN	Strada Țărăncuței 18, Fălticeni 725200, Romania	RO	caneparo.org	hemp fibre, hemp textiles	SME
FCM GLOBAL	Vereda Guamito El Capiro	CO	fcm-global	selling CBD formulations	SME
Filatura Lino e Canapa dell'Adige	Viale Lombardia 7, 20847 - Albiate (MB)	IT		hemp processing plants	SME
Fiori di Canapa	Strada Argine Zara 45, 46027 - San Benedetto Po (MN)	IT		hemp production	PERSON
FORMULA SWISS	Baar	CH	formulaswiss.com	nutraceutical selling	SME
Fracta Sativa Unisativa	Via Leopardi 80027, Frattamaggiore, Campania, Italy	IT	https://it-it.facebook.com/f	information/education	NGO
FRENKENBERGER HANFPRODUKTE	Take Hemp GmbH, Petersbergstrasse 6, A-5300 Hallwang	AT	https://frenkenberger.at	hemp food	Ristorante
Gatichanvre	12 Bis Rue de l'Essonne, 91720 PRUNAY sur ESSONNE	FR	https://gatichanvre.fr/	hemp building material, fil	SME
GENERAL HEMP MARKETING	ul. Kościelniaka 26a 41-409 Mysłowice	PL	gmhemp.pl	hemp manufacturer	SME
Genetia BioScience s.r.o.	Rudé armády 95, 289 13 Zvěřinek	CZ	www.genetia.cz	Cannabis clones	SME
Geochanvre	Rte de Frangey, 89160 Lézennes	FR	https://www.geochanvre.fr	hemp geotextile	
Global Hemp Service	4 allée du vieux jardin - croissy sur seine 78290, France	FR	https://www.globalhempse	hemp flowers, CBD produ	PERSON
Gmund	Mangfallstraße 5, 83703 Gmund am Tegernsee	D	https://world-en.gmund.co	hemp papar	
good system s.r.o.	Hviezdoslavovo nám. 1684/23, 02601 Dolný Kubín, Slovenská republika	SK	https://www.sum.sk	hemp food, cosmetics	
GREEN LANES	ul. View 10 50-052 Wrocław	PL	https://greenlanes.pl/	Green Lanes conducts re	RESEARCH
GreenHub s.r.o.	Slezská 949/32, 120 00 Praha 2	CZ	www.ghub.cz	Hemp flowers	SME
GRINLAND	Dusseldorf	DE	grinland.de		SME
H DROP	Roermondseweg 28 6081 NV Haelen	NL	hdrop.com	CBD based products proc	SME
Hahnemuehle	Hahnstraße 5, 37586 Dassel, Německo	DE	http://www.hahnemuehle.c	hemp paper	
Hanf farm	Dorfstraße 58, 17209 Melz	D	https://hanffarm.de	hemp food, machines	PERSON
HANF FARM	Dorfstr. 58 17209 melz	DE	hanffarm.de	cultivation	SME
Hanf fassen	Brüssower Allee 88, 17291 Prenzlau, Německo	D	https://www.hanffaser.de	hemp building	SME
Hanf museum	Mühlendamm 5, 10178 Berlin, Německo	DE	http://www.hanfmuseum.d	hemp museum	
Hanfland	Industriestraße, 3860, Rakousko	AT	https://www.hanfland.at	hemp food & feed	
HANFOSAN	Oroklini	CY	hanfosan.de		SME
hanfwerk Feinkostmanufaktur UG	Mühlendamm 5, 10178 Berlin	DE	https://www.hanfwerk.de/	hemp food	
Hanf-zeit	Lipper Tor 5, 32839 Steinheim, Germany	GE	https://hanf-zeit.com	hemp food, feed, cosmetics	
Happy canapa società agricola	Via S.P. Terlizzi-Giovinazzo Km 2, 70038 - Terlizzi (BA)	IT		hemp production and pro	SME
HAVACAN s.r.o.	Jiráskovo náměstí 1981/6, 120 00 Praha 2	CZ	www.havacan.com	Hemp flowers	SME
HEALTH PLANT PRODUCTS	Vlotlaan 605 2681 TZ Monster	NL	healthyplantproducts.nl	Healthy Plant Products p	SME
HEMP BOTANICS	37 High Street, Chatham, Kent, ME4 4EN.	GB	hempbotanics.com		SME
Hemp connect	Pastorenstraße 16 - 18, 20459 Hamburg	D	https://www.hempconnect	hemp food, hemp stem	SME
Hemp Factory s.r.o.	Klokotská 744/29, 390 01 Tábor	CZ	www.hempfactory.cz	Hemp flowers	SME
Hemp it	6, Rue Louis Lumière – Zone Actival, 49 250 BEAUFORT EN ANJOU	FR	https://www.hemp-it.coop	hemp farming seeds, R&D	
Hemp Juice Company BV	Raadhuisweg 11, 9665 JE Oude Pekela	NL	https://sanahempjuice.con	hemp food supplements	

Hemp production	Chraštica 7, 262 72 Březnice	CZ	https://hempcentrum.cz/kc	hemp food, hemp cosmet	SME
Hempage	Industriestraße 14, 91325 Adelsdorf, Německo	DE	https://www.hempage.de	hemp textile	
HempCluster	Družstevná 590/105, 97632 Badin	SK	https://www.hempcluster.e	hemp fibre, construction	NGO
HempConnect	Pastorenstraße 16 - 18, 20459 Hamburg, Germany	DE	https://www.hempconnect.	Hemp industry support	SME
Hempflax	Hendrik Westerstraat 20, 9665 AL Oude Pekela	NL	http://hempflax.com	Hemp flowers, cannabino	SME
HEMPFLAX	Hendrik Westerstraat 20, 9665 AL Oude Pekela,	DE	hempflax.com	hemp fibers and intermed	SME
Hempions	Bucherstraße 34, 6922 Wolfurt, Austria	AT	https://hempions.com	hemp food and cosmetics	
HEMP-IT	6, Rue Louis Lumière – Active area, 49 250 BEAUFORT EN ANJOU	FR	hemp-it.coop		COOP
HEMLAB SP	Pana Balcera 6 / 124 20-631 Lublin	PL	hemplab.pl		SME
HEMPMATE	Gersauerstrasse 78 CH-6440 Brunnen	CH	hempmate.com	premium CBD products	SME
Hempoint, s.r.o.	Hruškové dvory 116, 586 01 Jihlava	CZ	www.hempoint.cz	Hempseeds, hemp food,	SME
HEMPRO INTERNATIONAL		DE	hempro.com	all hemp product	SME
Hemp International Gmbh	Münsterstrasse 336, 40470 Düsseldorf, Germany	DE	https://www.hempro.com/	Hemp food, hemp seeds,	SME
HEMPSKA	Slovenská Konopárska Asociácia 044 45 Bidovce 206	SK		association	NGO
Hempstatic	Lindengasse 56 / 18-19, Vienna, 1070, Austria	AT	https://hempstatic.at/	hemp fibre, construction	SME
Hemptoday	Naklo 74, 42-235 Naklo	PL	http://hemptoday.net	international hemp	
Henry Hemp harvester	Hanover, Germany	GE	henryshempharvester.de	Hemp machine	
Herbs&Hydro	Al. Wojciecha Korfantego 81h/6-7, 40 160 Katowice, Poland	PL	https://pl.herbshydro.com	hemp cosmetics	
HOFIGAL EXPORT-IMPORT SA	Strada Intr. Serelor Nr. 2, Bucharest, 070000	RO	hofigal.eu	CBD product	SME
Hopfenveredlung St. Johann	Auenstraße 18-20 85283 Wolnzach	DE	nateco2.de		PERSON
House of Hemp AB	GÖTEBORG, Sweden	SWE	https://houseofhemp.se	hemp building	
HUNHEMP	Tapioszentmarton	HUN	hunhemp.hu		SME
Hylar	Vijvedreef 54, 8710 Sint-Baafs-Vijve, Belgium	BE	https://www.hylar.be/en/	machinery	
Development for Food Bioresources	6th Dinu Vintila Str., 2nd District, 021102, Bucharest, Romania	RO	bioresurse.ro	Hemp food	RTO
IBNA BALOTESTI	Șoseaua București-Ploiești 1, Balotești 077015	RO	ibna.ro	Hemp seeds	RTO
ICANNA – International Institute for Cannabinoids	Kodeljevo Castle, Ulica Carla Benza 16, 1000 Ljubljana, Slovenia	SL	https://www.institut-icanna	R&D	
ICPA Bucharest	Bd. Marasti, nr. 61, 011464 Bucuresti, ROMANIA	RO	icpa.ro	Hemp cultivation	RTO
IFA creation	7 RUE SAINT-NICOLAS 75012 PARIS	FR	https://www.ifa-creation.fr/	hemp textile	
IHEMPFARMS	BABA MOTA 2, 5000 VELIKO TARNOVO,	BG	https://www.ihempfarms.c	hemp food, hempseeds	
Il borgo della canapa	Podere Le Venelle, 58027 - Roccastrada (GR)	IT		hemp production	SME
Il Club della Canapa	Corso Garibaldi 111, 55100 - Lucca (LU)	IT		CBD and ricreative hemp	SME
Il laboratorio della Canapa	Via Torino 4, 10010 - Barone Canavese (TO)	IT		hemp production	SME
ILESOL	Varaždinska ulica 5, Jalkovec 42000 Varaždin	HR	ilesol.com		SME
IN MATRIX INTEGRATED SERVICES SRL		RO	http://victoria-mea.ro	CBD producer and seller	SME
Institute for Textiles and Leather	Lucretiu Patrascanu 16, sector 3, Bucharest, 030508	RO	incdtp.ro	Hemp geotextile	RTO
IND-AGRO-POL Cluster		RO	inma.ro/indagropol	supply chain	NGO
Ing. Ladislav Krajiča	Dlouhá 134, 763 15 Slušovice	CZ		Cannabis flower	PERSON
Development for Machines and Installations	6, Ion Ionescu de la Brad Blv., Sector 1, Bucharest, 013813, Romania	RO	inma.ro	R&D	RTO
Hydraulics and Pneumatic	14, Cutitul de Argint Street, district 4, Bucharest	RO	ihp.ro	R&D	RTO
Institute of Social Investigative Studies, z.s.	Jenečská 235/4, 161 00 Praha - Liboc	CZ	www.institutesis.com	Hemp flowers	NGO
Interchanvre	Rue des Giranaux, 70100 Gray, Francie	FR	https://www.interchanvre.c	hemp industry support	
ISLAZ SA	Str. Fabricii, 3, Alexandria, Teleorman, 140106, Alexandria	RO	islaz.ro	Machinery	SME
Isohemp	Rue George Cosse, 1, Z.I. Noville-Les-Bois, 5381 Fernelmont	BE	https://www.iso hemp.com/	Hemp buiding materials	SME
JACOB HOODY	Rijksweg 119 1906 BG Limmen	NL	jacob-hooy.com		SME
Jamaica canapa store	Via Inerio 35/C, 40126 - Bologna (BO)	IT		hemp production	SME
JM WHOLESALE	1 Brook Street Whetstone Leicester LE8 6LA	GB	jm-wholesale.co.uk	CBD selling	SME
KADENWOOD BIOSCIENCES	450 Newport Center Drive Suite 550 Newport Beach, CA 92660	USA	kadenwoodbiosciences.com		SME
KANNA STAR	Zbikowska 13 05-800 Pruszkow Poland	PL	kannastar.com	hemp extractor	SME
Kannabio	Skoufa 110, 38334, Volos	GR	https://www.kannabio.gr	hemp food, hemp flower, hemp cosmetics	
KANNAWAY	10525 Vista Sorrento Pkwy #200 San Diego, California, Stati Uniti d'America 92121	NL	kannaway.com	CBD producer and seller	SME
KATTY FASHION SRL	Calea Chișinăului 57, Iași 700179, Romania	RO	katty-fashion.com/	hemp fibre, hemp textile	SME
KD PHYTO	Via Campagna, 30 Bioggio, Tesino 6934 CH	DE	kdpharmagroup.com		LE

KIARA	gais	CH	kiaranaturals.com	SME
KND LABS	Lakewood, CO	USA	kndlabs.com	SME
Kobe-CZ	U Sladovny 430, 671 25 Hodonice	CZ	http://kobe-cz.eu	Hemp building material LE
Kombinat konopny	Berylowa 7F, 82-310 Gronowo Górne	PL	https://kombinatkonopny.pl	hemp fibre, hemp flower
KONOPLEX	107031, Moscow, Dmitrovsky Lane, 9	RU	konoplex.ru	industrial hemp producer SME
KONOPNICA	Tolstého 5 811 06 Bratislava	SK	konopnica.sk	CBD producer and seller SME
LABOCAN	Speijkerstraat 2, 5492NP Sint-Oedenrode, the Netherlands	NL	labocan.com	SME
Laroche	84 rue de Thizy BP21 COURS LA VILLE, 69470 COURS, France	FR	https://www.laroche.fr	machinery
Le vie della Canapa	Via Parma 15/B, 46100 - Mantova (MN)	IT		food, cosmetics from can:
Legalizace.cz, z.s.	Jaromírova 18, 128 00 Praha 2	CZ	www.legalizace.com	information/education NGO
Legaljoint-canapa del principato	Via Matteotti 84, 83030 - Prato di Principato Ultra (AV)	IT		hemp production, process SME
Leidi Canapa	Via Cella 11, 29121 - Piacenza (PC)	IT		production and selling of l SME
LEROS, s.r.o.	U Národní galerie 470, 156 00 Praha - Zbraslav	CZ	www.leros.com	Hemp flowers LE
LES CHANVRES DE L'ATLANTIQUE	52 rue du marensin 40230 Saint-Geours-de-Maremne	FR	nuntisunya.com	SME
LIQUID	Grunbacher Straße 59-65 71384 Weinstadt	DE	liquid-universum.com	multiple purpose hemp pr SME
LITTLERICK	White Cross Business Park, South Road, Lancaster,	GB	littlerick.co.uk	Leading CBD Drinks Man SME
Love canapa	Via Puccini 53, 50041 - Calenzano (FI)	IT		hemp products selling
Lucia Gogoláková	Spálená 92/21, 110 00 Praha 1	CZ		PERSON
Lukáš Stehno	Nám. Čsl. Legií 851, 530 02 Pardubice	CZ	www.apeos.cz	Social care PERSON
Mabeko, s.r.o.	Rousínov 47, 473 01 Svor	CZ	www.mabeko.com	Hemp building material SME
Magazin konopí	Na Folimance 2155/15, 120 00 Praha 2	CZ	https://magazin-konopi.cz	hemp, cannabinoids, pati SME
Master-CBD s.r.o.	Kloboučnická 1735/26, 140 00 Praha 4	CZ	www.mastercbd.cz	Hemp flowers, clones, cai SME
MAX HEMP	ul. Borowska 242 50-558 Wroclaw	PL	maxhemp.pl	SME
MECANICA CEAHLAU SA	Piatra Neamt, 6th Dumbravei Street, Neamt County	RO	mecanicaceahlau.ro	Machinery SME
Meditativa la canapa sativa	Via Marsala 2, 87046 - Montalto Uffugo (CS)	IT	www.lacanapasativa.it	hemp production and res SME
MH MEDICAL HEMP	Muensterstrasse 334 40470 Duesseldorf	DE	medicalhemp.com	CBD producer SME
MilenTech	Sat Breazu, Comuna Rediu, Judet Iasi 70740	RO		hemp farming SME
MilenTech	Sat Breazu, Comuna Rediu, Judet Iasi 70740	RO	caneparo.org	hemp farming SME
MOLLERUP GODS	Møllerupvej 26 8410 Rønde	DNK	moellerupgods.dk	SME
Moravian Hemp s.r.o.	U Tiskárny 616/9, 702 00 Ostrava - Přívoz	CZ	www.moravianhemp.cz	Hemp flowers, hemp food SME
MPI SOLUTIONS	De Bouw 1-A 3991 SX Houten	NL	mpi.eu	We fill your CBD-oil in hai SME
MUDr. Pavel Kubů	Benešovská 32, 100 00 Praha 10	CZ		PERSON
Museum de Caňamo	Carrer Ample, 35, 08002 Barcelona, Španělsko	ES	http://hashmuseum.com/	hemp museum
MVDr. Radek Staněk	A. Dvořáka 926/7, 751 31 Lipník nad Bečvou	CZ		Hemp flowers PERSON
myCBD	Gran de Gràcia 15, 1 ^o -1 ^a 08012. Barcelona	ES	mycbd.com	SME
Naporo	Auggenthal 158, 2054 Auggenthal	AT	https://www.hanfdaemmur	hemp building material
National School Du Chanvre	3 Rue des Tourdres, 48000 Mende, Francie	FR	http://www.ecolenationale.fr	hemp school
Natura solution - l'emporio della canapa	Via Scazzola 36, 15121 - Alessandria (AL)	IT		multiple purpose hemp pr SME
Natural canapa	Via Calabria 13, 88051 - Cropani (CZ)	IT		hemp production
NATURALPES	9 Rue des Cèdres, 1920 Martigny	CH	naturalpes.ch	CBD producer SME
NATURE CELL	Kristiansvej 13 8660 Skanderborg	DNK	naturecell.com	SME
NATURE CURE	Kabelstraat 4 1749 DM Warmenhuizen	NL	naturecure.eu	CBD producer SME
Nektar	Weberstrasse 6, 3300 Amstetten, Austria	AT	https://nektar.at/produkte/	hemp cosmetics
NORDIC OIL	Octhen	NL	nordicoil.de	CBD producer SME
Nunti Sunya	Zoomalia, 52 rue du marensin zone Atlantisud à côté de, 40230 Saint-Geours-de-Maremne, Francie	FR	https://www.nuntisunya.com	hemp textile
Obelisk farm	Gulbj, Obeliškas, LV-4614	LV	https://www.obeliskfarm.lv	hemp food
Obermuhle	Tiefenbach 21,3851 Kautzen, Austria	AT	https://www.obermuehle.at	hemp sheets, matrac

Ondřej Solar	Podolí 115, 664 03	CZ	Hemp	PERSON
Opificio della canapa	Via Fattori 38, 59021 - Vaiano (PO)	IT	hemp production	SS
Orto e canapa	Via Bassiano 217, 04018 - Sezze (LT)	IT	hemp production	II
Parenteral a.s.	Přívozní 2/1054, 17000 Praha 7	CZ	https://www.cutishelp.com hemp cosmetics	LE
PBG GLOBAL	Byalo pole 3 street, 1618 Sofia, Bulgaria	BG	pbg.global	SME
Pensieri di canapa	Via Mazzini 144, 55100 - Lucca (LU)	IT	paper and fibers production	II
PHARMACORP INNOVATION SRL	Bucharest	RO	pharmacorp.ro hemp cosmetics	SME
PHYTOPUR BIO	/	GB	phytopurbio.com CBD producer	SME
Planet chanvre	Bellevue RD 402 - 77120 Aulnoy	FR	http://planetechanvre.com hemp building material, fc	SME
PLANTINE	Coolsingel 6, 3011 AD Rotterdam,	NL	plantine.com	SME
Podlaskie konopie	Dobrzyniówka 63a, 16-060 Dobrzyniówka, Polsko	PL	http://www.podlaskiekonopie.pl hemp building, fibre, shives	
PRODIN SA	Strada Vâlsânești 1, București, Romania	RO	www.tesaturisanatoase.ro hemp fibre, hemp textile	SME
Produttori Canapa Italiana (assocanapa)	Via Morello 2/A, 10022 - Carmagnola (TO)	IT	www.assocanapa.it	SME
Progetto Canapa	Via Burchietti 14, 50018 - Scandicci (FI)	IT	textile production	SME
PROTECT PHARMA	Venoseva 1c 31540 Rakitovica	HR	protect-pharma.hr	SME
Puglia canapa	Via Satriano POD. 689, 71122 - Foggia (FG)	IT	www.pugliacanapacbd.it CBD and ricreative hemp	SME
Pura Vida Cosmetics	Ul. dr. Luje Naletilića 57, 10020, Zagreb, Chorvatsko	CRO	https://vida-organic.com hemp cosmetics	
RAINBOW	80, Rue des Haies, Paris, 75020, Paris	FR	be-rainbow.com	SME
Repubblica della canapa	Via di Casanello 60/C, 73100 - Lecce (LE)	IT	www.schiesana.com	II
Rete canapa sicilia	Viale Mattei 16, 93012 - Gela (CL)	IT	hemp production	ONG
RO Challenges		RO	caneparo.org hemp processing	SME
RURIS IMPEX SRL	CALEA SEVERINULUI NR. 10 BL. 317B, AP. Parter, 200233 CRAIOVA	RO	ruris.ro Machinery	SME
RX PHARMATECH	Unit 23 Pit Cliffway, Bradford, BD5 7SG	GB	allaboutcbd.co.uk	SME
Sa canapa	Via Maista Caria 19, 09070 - Seneghe (OR)	IT	hemp production	SS
Salento Canapa	Via Sant'Anna 86, 73029 - Vernole (LE)	IT	hemp production	II
SANOBIOTEC	Mokslininku g. 12 LT-08412 Vilnius	LT	sanobiotec.com development, production	SME
Santa canapa	Via Tamburi, 86170 - Isernia (IS)	IT	hemp production	II
Sardegna canapa società agricola	Viale Italia 14, 07100 - Sassari (SS)	IT	hemp production	SME
SATIMED	86-90 Paul Street London, EC2A 4NE	LT	satimed.eu research and production	SME
SATIPHARM	/	IRL	satipharm.com development and manufa	
SensiQure s.r.o.	Jizerská 851, 196 00 Praha 9	CZ	www.sensisure.com Hemp flowers, cannabino	SME
SERPLUS		RO	caneparo.org hemp building	SME
SERVOPLANT SRL	Șoseaua Odăii 15, București 013601, Romania	RO	servoplant.ro Machinery	SME
SIGNATURE PRODUCTS	Klumpensee 2 75177 Pforzheim	DE	signature-products.com hemp supplier	SME
Società agricola Canapa del Grappa	Via Bassanese 69, 31037 - Loria (TV)	IT	hemp production	SS
Società agricola canapa felix	Via Farina 51, 80056 - Ercolano (NA)	IT	hemp production	SME
Società agricola canapa green	Viale del Lavoro 5/A, 08023 - Fonnì (NU)	IT	hemp production	SS
società agricola canapa light	Via Gramsci 8, 08018 - Sindia (NU)	IT	hemp production	SS
Società agricola canapa logudoro	Via Roma 48, 07044 - Ittiri (SS)	IT	hemp production	SME
Società agricola Canapa Sativa S.r.l.	Via Monte Napoleone 8, 20121 - Milano (MI)	IT	hemp production	SME
società agricola ciuri di canapa	Via Ricciardi 6, 90047 - Partinico (PA)	IT	hemp production	SS
Società agricola cristal canapa	Via Matteotti 19, 37057 - San Giovanni Lupatoto (VR)	IT	hemp production	SS
Società agricola Lessinia Green Canapa	Via Cona 10, 37020 - Sant'Anna d'Alfaedo (VR)	IT	hemp production	SS
Società agricola Mondo Canapa	Via De Gasperi 6, 24031 - Almenno San Salvatore (BG)	IT	hemp production	SS

società agricola P.S.G. canapa sardegna	Via De Gasperi 3, 08020 - Lula (NU)	IT		hemp production	SS
Società italiana canapa	Piazza Buenos Aires 20 - 00198 - Roma (RM)	IT		hemp production	SME
Società semplice agricola della canapa	Viale degli Astri 30, 00144 - Roma (RM)	IT		hemp production	SME
Soluzione Canapa	Via Briante 22, 21019 - Somma Lombardo (VA)	IT		CBD and ricreative hemp	II
SOUTH HEMP	Contrada Casellone snc, Crispiano (TA)	IT	southern.it		SME
staffolani global canapa	Contraa Santa Nigrilli 3/A, 89042 - Gioiosa Ionica (RC)	IT		hemp production	II
Station of Agricole Research-Development Lovrin	Str. Main no. 200, Loc. Lovrin, County Timis	RO	scdalovrin.com	hemp farming seeds, R&I	RTO
Secuieni Neamt	Principală nr.377, com. Secuieni, județul Neamț, România	RO	www.scd.ro/	hemp farming seeds, R&I	RTO
Svatý Sedláček s.r.o.	Čechova1247/679001 Jeseník	CZ	https://svatysedlacek.cz	Hemp flowers, cannabino	SME
Tatham	The Grange Industrial Park, Farnham Road, Bradford, BD7 3JG, United Kingdom	UK	http://tatham-uk.com	machinery	
Terre di canapa	Via Comunale Santo, 98148 - Messina (ME)	IT		hemp production	II
Teverina canapa light	Strada Teverina 9, 01020 - Celleno (VT)	IT		hemp production	II
					SME
THE HEMP COMPANY DUBLIN	167 Capel Street, Dublin 1	IRL	hemppcompany.ie		SME
					SME
THE HOUSE OF GREEN	Route de la Garenne, St Peter Port, Guernsey, Channel Islands, GY1 2RH	GB	thehouseofgreen.gg		
The Institute of Natural Fibres and Medicinal Plant	ul. Wojska Polskiego 71b, 60-630 Poznan	PL	https://iwnirz.pl	hemp farming seeds, R&D, textile	
TRICHOME PHARMA	Av. de Europa, 34D, 28023, Madrid	ES	trichomepharma.com	cultivation, processing an	SME
Univeristy Aurel Vlaicu Arad	B-dul Revoluției, nr. 77, 310130 Arad, România	RO	uav.ro/en/academic/scient	hemp farming seeds, R&I	RTO
Medicine „Ion Ionescu de la Brad” Iasi	Aleea Mihail Sadoveanu nr.3, Iasi 700490, Romania	RO	www.uaiasi.ro/	hemp fibre, machinery	RTO
				Information/education	RTO
University of Craiova	Strada Alexandru Ioan Cuza 13, Craiova 200585	RO	ucv.ro		
VICTORIA MEA ASSOCIATION		RO	http://victoriamea.ro	medical cannabis	NGO and RD
Villa canapa	Via Madonna 70, 41011 - Campogalliano (MO)	IT		agri-tourism	II
Virs Canapa Agricola	Via Fillide 54, 00155 - Roma (RM)	IT		hemp production	SME
VITRASAN	Pirching 95/1 A-8200 Gleisdorf	AT	vitrasan.com		SME
Vivere la canapa	Via Carluccio 10, 73037 - Poggiardo (LE)	IT		hemp production	II
Výzkumný ústav potravinářství Praha v.v.i.	Radiová 7, 170 00 Praha 7 – Holešovice, 102 00 Praha 10	CZ	www.vupp.cz	Hemp food	RD
weedgreen canapa	Via Cagliari N. 267 99, 09122 - Cagliari (CA)	IT		hemp production	II
ZELENA ZEME	Wuchterlova 523/5 6.patro 160 00, Praha 6, Česko	CZ	zelenazeme.cz		SME
Zelena Země	Zelená Země s.r.o., Wuchterlova 523/5, 160 00 Praha 6	CZ	https://www.zelenazeme.c	hemp food, hemp cosmet	SME
ZWEI ZEHN	Kotzenbach 2, 92715 Püchersreuth	DE	zwei-zehn.com		SME